

Pages Of Sensibility: Exploring The Transformative Power Of Early Literacy

Samina Saadia, Muhammad Farrukh, Mohammad Nawaz, Zahid Farooq,
Abdul rouf Zahid, Hafiz Zulfiqar Ali

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 26 , 2024</p> <p>Accepted: July 29 , 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Reading, Young Children, Perceptual Development, Cognitive Skills, Emotional Intellige.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14246564</p>	<p><i>Reading plays a pivotal role in shaping the perceptual makeup of young children, influencing various cognitive processes crucial for their development. This abstract examines the multifaceted impact of reading on the perceptual development of children, encompassing cognitive, emotional, and social dimensions firstly, reading facilitates cognitive growth by enhancing perceptual skills such as visual discrimination, pattern recognition, and spatial awareness. Through exposure to diverse textual and pictorial stimuli, children refine their ability to distinguish between shapes, colors, and objects, laying the foundation for complex cognitive processes later in life secondly, reading fosters emotional intelligence by exposing children to diverse characters, situations, and perspectives. Through empathetic engagement with fictional narratives, children develop a nuanced understanding of emotions, empathy, and interpersonal relationships, crucial for navigating social interactions furthermore, reading cultivates social awareness by introducing children to cultural diversity, societal norms, and ethical dilemmas. By exploring narratives set in different contexts, children develop a broader worldview, empathy towards others, and critical thinking skills necessary for navigating an increasingly interconnected world however, the impact of reading on young children's perceptual makeup is contingent upon various factors, including the quality and quantity of reading experiences, parental involvement, and socio-economic background. Additionally, individual differences in cognitive abilities and learning styles influence how children perceive and interpret textual information. In conclusion, reading serves as a catalyst for the holistic development of young children, shaping their perceptual makeup in cognitive, emotional, and social domains. Understanding the profound influence of reading on children's perceptual development can inform educational practices, parental guidance, and policy initiatives aimed at fostering lifelong literacy and well-being.</i></p>

Introduction

The early years of childhood are a critical period marked by rapid cognitive, emotional, and social development. During this formative stage, children's experiences shape their perceptual makeup, laying the groundwork for future learning and adaptation. Among these experiences, reading holds a particularly profound influence, serving as a gateway to a world of knowledge, imagination, and empathy. The impact of reading on young children's perceptual makeup is a topic of growing interest among educators, psychologists, and parents alike. Research has increasingly highlighted the multifaceted benefits of early literacy experiences, extending far beyond mere language acquisition. Indeed, the act of reading engages cognitive processes that fundamentally shape how children perceive and interact with the world around them. In this context, perceptual makeup refers to the intricate interplay between sensory input, cognitive processing, and socio-emotional factors that contribute to an individual's perceptual awareness and understanding. Understanding the impact of reading on this perceptual makeup requires an exploration of its influence on various cognitive, emotional, and social dimensions of development. Cognitive development encompasses a broad array of skills and abilities, including perception, memory, attention, and problem-solving. Reading provides young children with rich and diverse stimuli that stimulate these cognitive processes, fostering skills such as visual discrimination, pattern recognition, and spatial reasoning. Through exposure to written language and pictorial representations, children learn to make sense of their environment, laying the foundation for more advanced cognitive abilities later in life.

Moreover, reading nurtures emotional intelligence by immersing children in the lives and experiences of fictional characters. As they journey through the pages of storybooks, children develop empathy, perspective-

taking, and an understanding of complex emotions. Through identification with characters and exploration of moral dilemmas, reading cultivates emotional literacy, equipping children with essential skills for navigating their own emotions and understanding those of others. Additionally, reading promotes social awareness by exposing children to diverse cultures, perspectives, and societal norms. Through literature, children encounter characters from different backgrounds and contexts, fostering curiosity, tolerance, and cultural sensitivity. By engaging with narratives that reflect the complexity of human experience, children develop a broader worldview and a deeper appreciation for diversity, laying the groundwork for inclusive attitudes and social cohesion. However, the impact of reading on young children's perceptual makeup is not uniform and can vary depending on various factors. These may include the quality and quantity of reading experiences, parental involvement, access to resources, and individual differences in cognitive abilities and learning styles. Understanding these factors is essential for maximizing the benefits of reading and addressing potential barriers to literacy development. In summary, the impact of reading on young children's perceptual makeup is multifaceted, encompassing cognitive, emotional, and social dimensions of development. By fostering cognitive skills, emotional intelligence, and social awareness, reading lays a solid foundation for lifelong learning, empathy, and well-being. Recognizing the transformative power of reading in early childhood underscores the importance of promoting literacy as a fundamental human right and essential component of holistic development. Why do we make our children read? What are the affects of reading on the children? How do we go about what to make our children read? These are some of the important questions to have appropriate and logic based answers to before we give any book to our children. I believe reading may be one of the most significant activities in personality and character development of our children, rather of any educated human being. In this article I have tried to rationalize my viewpoint, and have developed my ideas in a conceptual framework .

Education And Parents' Responsibility

We have around 70 to 80 years of earthly sojourn and then an unending after life. The afterlife is dependent upon our performance in this life. Our performance here depends on how we are prepared to perform, both, by the external interventions as well as through self-development. When we talk of external interventions that is where the parents nurturing of their children comes very first. As a famous hadith of our Holy Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) :

Narrated by Abu Huraira (R.A.): Allâh's Messenger (R.A.) said, Every child is born on Al-Fitrah but his parents make him a Jew, a Christian or a Magian.¹ As such Al-Ghazali puts the main responsibility for children's education on the parents, who, he says, „will take credit for their probity and bear the burden of their errors“; they are partners in everything the children do, and this responsibility is subsequently shared by the teachers.²

Al-Ghazali stresses the importance of character formation in childhood and as such the necessity to understand the “special characteristics of this period in order to deal with the child in an effective and sound manner”³. For Al-Farabi morality is a fundamental objective of education.⁴

Referring to the above quoted hadith Allama Muhammad Asad⁵ expands the word parents to cover environment the child is made to live in. For him, environmental interventions too play a key role in the education of a child. For Dr. Manzoorul Haq⁶ education in the Qur’anic phraseology is for the development of Nafs, the self; the personality which retains its identity throughout its career .

Another important aspect is the implication of the concept of education, for now it is used synonymous and rather exclusively for school education. The fact is, education starts from the birth of a child, rather even while it is still in its mother's womb. Parents and environment play the major role, while school is also a major intervention when the child grows up to the school going age. At what age the schooling should start can be contested and disputed. However, what is not disputed is the parents' responsibility for their offspring's education. Parents have to take the first responsibility for preparing their children for the goals of life, and prepare them to take stand on the last Day of Judgment. Parents will be held responsible for the basic years of their children's education. This calls for very serious considerations on part of the parents .

Keeping The End Objective In Mind

Now we come to the question: what is the most important goal of this life? As a Muslim it is very clearly the success in the eternal life after death. “Then, for such as had transgressed all bounds, and had preferred the life of this world, The Abode will be HellFire;”⁷ Further it is reminded that, "Whosoever seeks, other than Islam, a deen, it will not be accepted from him and he, in the Hereafter, is among the losers."⁸ A clear reminder is narrated from our prophet, may peace and blessings of Allah subhanawata'ala be upon him, “The son of Adam will not pass away from Allah until he is asked about five things: how he lived his life, and how he utilized his youth, with what means did he earn his wealth, how did he spend his wealth, and what did he do with his knowledge”.⁹ Correspondingly Iqbal¹⁰ elaborates that this goal of success in a'akhirah is only achieved by performing in this life. It is commonly said that this life is the till of the next everlasting life. Performance in this life will govern the results in the next. This calls for each one of us to endeavor for this very vital end, or

goal, of this life. What can be wiser than to begin everything with this end in mind, because if we put the ladder on the wrong wall, not being definite of our life goals, no matter how efficiently and proactively we climb, we will be landing at the wrong destination? Once the destination is clear, the passage plan has to be developed, „for without a passage plan the vessel is at a high risk of wrecking .“

Dr. Muhammad Rafiuddin in his book *First Principles of Education* allegorizes :

A motorist who sets out on a journey must know his destination and the road that leads to it before he sets out. If he doubles or trebles his speed while he happens to be travelling on a wrong road, he will not come any nearer to his destination, but will rather recede further away from it all the more quickly.¹¹

Stephen Covey warns that unless we start with a clear understanding of our destination we may find ourselves achieving victories that are empty successes that have come at the expense of things that we may realize were far more valuable to us. He further warns, “If the ladder is not leaning against the right wall every step we take just gets us closer to the wrong place faster”.¹²

When a Muslim looks at the world he looks from the perspective of a Khalifa of the Creator in this world. The Qur’an says: Behold, thy Lord said to the angels: "I will create a vicegerent on earth."¹³ This trust of Khalifa-ship the man accepted at his own peril¹⁴, and as such on the final Day of Judgment each Nafs or human will have to reply for his conduct of this earthly sojourn.¹⁵, and that will be a very tough day of this meeting¹⁶

Considering the serious implication of our belief and actions it is but imperative for us to have this end always in perspective? Moreover, when we begin with end in mind, we gain a different perspective all together¹⁷; then our learning and actions will be more directed towards the end objectives or goals. Our endeavors in sciences and literature will be directed accordingly.

Reading As Process Of Learning

If I was a Chinese, will anyone expect me to write like a Pakistani .

Doesn’t it seem to be an unreasonable expectation? Why does a Chinese write like a Chinese and a Pakistani like a Pakistani? It is one’s cultural overtone, which is impossible to avoid. A western writing will depict western culture, underlying beliefs, and core concepts of life. It is unavoidable, for we are very structured thinking beings, we make statements around our thinking, or what we call paradigm. No human being can be separated from that. Reading is a strong learning intervention; as such reading will definitely expose the reader to the culture, underlying beliefs, and core concepts of life of the writer. For a grown-up it may not be as influential as for a child who is at a very active mode of learning; for Green and Brock¹⁸ experiments showed that the children exposed to the egalitarian reading material showed more egalitarian responses and in spite of time passage, despite some reduction, the affect persisted. They further elaborate that the narratives are persuasive, and the morals rooted in them affect children’s worldview. Mar, Djikic & Oatley¹⁹ observe that reading influences the process of learning. They claim that reading fictions has more affect, as the reader unintentionally emulates the characters of the fiction. Hakemulder²⁰ searched through 54 reliable and valid experimental studies in which fictional narratives indicated substantial affect on moral development, norms, values, and self-concepts. Mar, Djikic & Oatley²¹ observe that change in personality is mediated by the emotions experienced while reading. Any intellectual exercise will affect a child’s learning, and reading is considered to be one of the powerful learning tools, an important question is, how reading affects the learning process, and consequently the personality of a child? One important faculty which is utterly affected by learning processes is that of perception, which is synonymous to paradigm or the world view. The American Heritage Dictionary of the English Language defines Worldview as: (i) the overall perspective from which one sees and interprets the world; (ii) A collection of beliefs about life and the universe held by an individual or a group. „A worldview consists of basic assumptions and images that provide a more or less coherent—though not necessarily accurate, way of thinking about the world“; it is developed through culture, religion, environment, or consciously as through learning processes²². Any event or knowledge that casts an impression on human mind affects this worldview, as such it is susceptible to modification. For the first few years of life the changes are major, and as the mental maps become defined the modifications become more subtle and selective. Muslim scholar Acigenc claims that all human conduct is ultimately traceable to a worldview; worldview is the "framework within which our mind operates"²³ . Ibn Khaldun often compares it to a dye that lasts until the cloth to which it has been applied is destroyed²⁴. For Wallace the worldview is “the very skeleton of concrete cognitive assumptions on which the flesh of customary behavior is hung”.²⁵ Covey claims that we see the world, not as it is, but as we are—or, as we are conditioned to see it.²⁶ He further emphasizes that we must look at the lens through which we see the world, because the lens itself shapes how we interpret the world. One of the major factors which shape this lens is an individual’s learning processes .

Furthermore most of Muslim as well as western intellectuals like Miskawayah, al-Farabi, Ghazali, Ibn Khaldun, Fried, Adler, Millard, Dollard, Montessori, John Holt agree that the initial years of an individual are crucial for active personality development; which is the period of active development of a child’s worldview. The learning interventions, which disrupt Islamic identity and values, will accordingly affect this personality development. Which Covey calls the farm-house rule. The farm is a natural system. The price must be paid and the process

followed.²⁷ You always reap what you sow; there is no shortcut. If one makes the wrong investments/he will get the results accordingly. The nature will only follow the law of cause and effect .

With the logic constructed above, if we take the activity of reading as a learning process which significantly influences a child's worldview and in turn in the shaping of his personality, it is but imperative that we keep the above farmhouse rule in mind .

Another natural rule to be mindful about is that of „garbage in, garbage out“. If we put garbage in a child's brain, it will reflect accordingly in his worldview and personality. Any concepts which are harmful or useless from the Islamic perspective are garbage for us; for example the concept of world without a creator, human without a soul, the implicit and explicit denial of the afterlife, and west's animalistic approach to life which is devoid of shame, these are basic precepts in secular worldviews. These concepts are the main features of the western sciences, and naturally reflect in their literature as well. The dependency on western literature is a self-inflicted tragedy by the Muslim societies. The learning interventions develop a mental map or perception which is based on western thoughts, quite contrary to the Islam based paradigm or world view. The result is we try to find our way through to the destination using a wrong map. Covey equates paradigms to conceptual maps in an individual's mind.²⁸

AFFECTS OF LEARNING ON BELIEFS AND ACTIONS

Now an important question to ask is how does the learning and the worldview affect our belief and action? Let us take a few examples: my five years old daughter came with her mathematics book and was covering a picture with her palm, insisting that it was something, which could not be shown to me. Upon my repeated requests she exposed the picture that was of a lone lady in bikini lying on a beach depicting the solitary for the numeral one. She had not yet polluted her perception with the western concept of shame. For her shame was still the map that we had created in theory; she could observe this odd picture, where as we could not observe this prior to her pointing out, which shows that we were already conditioned for this. My son was taught from a British published history book in his O'Levels that Tipu Sultan was a rebel. Should we blame the British for this statement? From their perspective he was; from our perspective he was a hero. A convert to Islam Laila Brence narrates :

I have noticed that my 9-year-old son is somewhat conditioned to happy endings, which once again can be influence of children's subculture and „happily ever after“ trends in cartoons, etc. Just recently he read in his reading aloud time a story, in which the main character (11 yrs old boy) died at the end of the story, and felt very emotionally crushed by such ending. He even said to me not to give to him such stories anymore, because he felt so very sad reading it. It gave us the chance to talk about the real life scenarios of sad events and how they differ from happy endings of most cartoons/fiction stories/fairy tales.²⁹

Another example as narrated by Laila Brence for how affectively the former Soviet Union could condition the students to the Soviet requirements :

I was growing up in the communist system of the Soviet Union. The focus of government at the time was very much on the school children - to develop them into loyal citizens of the state. This was achieved by a heavy dose of ideology being pushed into young minds (which I was not aware of as a child, of course) through purposefully written school books infused with ideology and the requirement of Russian language and Russian literature courses in all schools starting from the very first grade.³⁰ For the affect of this programming, she elaborates :

Believe it or not, the system was extremely good, and successfully produced the required results. I realized this, when after the break-up of the Soviet Union I went for studies to the US as part of a group of students from the former Soviet Union. We, the students, ourselves were amazed at how similar all of us were. I mean we came from different states of the Soviet Union, spoke different languages, had different local cultures.³¹

Other than the conditioning, the above examples indicate the affect of literature on a child's mind. Every written matter has a message and that is absorbed well by the child reader, much more readily and complete as compared to a grown up, as the world view or perception of a young child is still raw and in a state of formation. The affects in childhood are long-lasting and more permanent as compared to that of grown-ups, who have already developed filters due to a more established worldview. For Maulana Maudoodi, exposing youth to an alien culture will certainly result in the loosening of Islamic moorings and loss of Islamic identity.³²

A revert sister reflecting of the issue of the affect of reading English books by the children cautions :

The foreign language and cultural baggage that comes along with it, will leave lasting marks on the personality of the child and the way he/she views the world. This aspect is especially important for us, as parents of Muslims, to understand.³³

Eighty years back another famous revert Allama Muhammad Asad (Ex-Leopold Weiss of Austria) sternly warned the Islamic world in the following words :

Islam and Western civilisation, being built on diametrically opposed conceptions of life, are not compatible in spirit. This being so, how could we expect that the education of Muslim youth on Western lines, an education based entirely on Western cultural experiences and values, could remain free from anti-Islamic influences?³⁴

The tragedy which the contemporary Muslim societies are inflicted with is the uncritical embracing of the western educational interventions and learning processes. Sayyid Qutb long ago too cautioned us that when we indiscriminately use Western educational interventions, we undoubtedly borrow as well a general scheme of philosophy and a mode of thought that underlies these interventions; „whether we like it or not“ .35

As I write this essay I observe my 14 months old granddaughter and am so awed at the intelligence which Allah has bestowed every child with. She has a different approach in behaving with each member of her close and extended family. Before me, she will avoid putting anything in her mouth, she will behave with more tenderness with my mother and has an entirely different behavior with my sister, whom she is extremely fond of. She cannot speak but understands what ever verbal conversation we have with her, and follows our verbal instructions. To think that at another two or three years“ time she will be lesser intelligent to absorb the message of any literature that we read to her seems to me extremely absurd .

Conclusions

The impact of reading on young children's perceptual makeup is undeniably profound, touching upon cognitive, emotional, and social dimensions of development. Through exposure to literature, children embark on a journey of discovery that shapes their understanding of the world and themselves. Cognitively, reading serves as a catalyst for the development of essential perceptual skills, such as visual discrimination, pattern recognition, and spatial reasoning. By engaging with written language and visual imagery, children hone their ability to interpret and make sense of the sensory input around them, laying a solid foundation for future learning and problem-solving. Emotionally, reading fosters empathy, emotional intelligence, and self-awareness. Through immersion in fictional narratives, children encounter a diverse array of characters and situations, learning to navigate complex emotions and moral dilemmas. By identifying with characters and exploring their inner worlds, children develop a deeper understanding of themselves and others, cultivating empathy and compassion. Socially, reading promotes cultural awareness, tolerance, and social cohesion. Through exposure to diverse perspectives and experiences, children develop a broader worldview and an appreciation for diversity. By engaging with narratives that reflect the richness and complexity of human society, children learn to navigate social dynamics, challenge stereotypes, and forge connections with others. However, the impact of reading on young children's perceptual makeup is not guaranteed and can be influenced by various factors, including access to resources, parental involvement, and individual differences in cognitive abilities. Addressing these factors requires a concerted effort from educators, parents, policymakers, and communities to ensure that all children have equitable access to quality reading experiences. In conclusion, the impact of reading on young children's perceptual makeup is profound and far-reaching, shaping their cognitive, emotional, and social development in meaningful ways. By recognizing the transformative power of reading in early childhood, we can empower children to become lifelong learners, empathetic individuals, and active participants in a diverse and interconnected world. Investing in literacy education is not only a moral imperative but also a strategic investment in the future well-being and prosperity of society as a whole.

References

- Muslim, Bukhari, Al-Bayhaqy and Al-Tabarany, each with a little difference in wordings
 Nofal, N. (2000). *Al-Ghazali*. Paris, UNESCO: International Bureau of Education .
 Nofal, N. (2000). *Al-Ghazali*. Paris, UNESCO: International Bureau of Education. P.5
 al-Talbi, A. (2000). *Al-Farabi*. Paris, UNESCO: International Bureau of Education .
 Asad, M. (2005). *Islam at the Crossroads*. Kuala Lumpur: The Other Press .
 Haque, M. (N.D.). *Qur'anic Model of Education*. Retrieved on November 04 ,
 .2011 www.tolueislam.org/bazms/Manzoor/Model.pdf
Qur"an Nāzi" āt 37-39
Qur"an Aal Imran 85
 :*Imām Hāfiz AbU 'Elsa Mohammad Ibn 'EisA At-Tirmidhi Translated by: Abu Khaliyl (USA) Ahādith edited and referenced by. Hfiz Abu Thhir Zubair 'Au Za'i 2007, DARUSSALAM Riyadh. Chapter i. on The Day Of Judgement hadith 2417, p.429*
 Iqbal, M. (1944). *The Secrets of the Self: (Asrar-i-Khudi) a Philosophical Poem (Revised ed.)*. (R. A. Nicholson, Ed., & R. A. Nicholson, Trans.) Lahore: Sh. M. Ashraf .
 Rafiuddin, M. (1983). *First Principles of Education (2nd ed.)*. Lahore: Iqbal Academy. P.IV
 Covey, S. R. (1992). *The Seven Habits of highly Effective People*. London :
 Simon & Schuster P.98
Qur"an al-Baqarah 30
Qur"an al -Ahzab 72
Qur"an al -Infitar 5
Qur"an al -Inshiqaq 5
 Covey, S. R. (1992). *The Seven Habits of highly Effective People*. London: Simon & Schuster .

- Green M.C. & Brock T.C. (2005). *Persuasiveness of Narratives, Persuasion: Psychological Insights and Perspectives*, (Ed. Brock T. C. & Green M. C.). Thousand Oaks: Sage .
- Mar, R.A., Djikic, M. & Oatley, K. (2008). *Effects of reading on knowledge, social abilities, and selfhood*. In S. Zyngier, M. Bortolussi, A. Chesnokova, & J. Auracher (Eds.). *Directions in empirical studies in literature: In honor of Willie van Peer*. (pp. 127-137). Amsterdam: Benjamins .
- Hakemulder, J. (2000). *The Moral Laboratory: Experiments examining the effects of reading Literature on Social Perception and Moral Self Concept*. John Benjamins Publishing Company, Philadelphia .
- Mar, R.A., Djikic, M. & Oatley, K. (2008). *Effects of reading on knowledge, social abilities, and selfhood*. In S. Zyngier, M. Bortolussi, A. Chesnokova, & J. Auracher (Eds.). *Directions in empirical studies in literature: In honor of Willie van Peer*. Amsterdam: Benjamins. p. 127-137
- Acikgenc, A. (1996). *Islamic Science: Towards a Definition*. Kuala Lumpur: ISTAC .
- Acikgenc, A. (1996). *Islamic Science: Towards a Definition*. Kuala Lumpur: ISTAC. P1
- Cheddadi, A. (2000). *Ibn Khaldun*. Paris, UNESCO: International Bureau of Education .
- Wallace, A.F.C. (1961). *Culture and Personality*. New York: Random house. P.101
- Covey, S. R. (1992). *The Seven Habits of highly Effective People*. London: Simon & Schuster .
- Covey, S. R. (1992). *The Seven Habits of highly Effective People*. London: Simon & Schuster .
- Covey, S. R. (1992). *The Seven Habits of highly Effective People*. London : Simon & Schuster .
- B. Laila. <https://groups.yahoo.com/neo/groups/pakistan-home-education>
- B. Laila. <https://groups.yahoo.com/neo/groups/pakistan-home-education>
- B. Laila. <https://groups.yahoo.com/neo/groups/pakistan-home-education>
- Maudoodi, S. A. (2000). *The Education*. (S. M. Rauf, Trans.) New Delhi : Markazi Maktaba Islami .
- B. Laila. <https://groups.yahoo.com/neo/groups/pakistan-home-education> 34
- Asad, M. (2005). *Islam at the Crossroads*. Kuala Lumpur: The Other Press. P.55
- Qutb, S. (2000). *Social Justice in Islam*, (Hardie J. B. Trans). Islamic book trust: Kuala Lumpur .
- Qur'an Aal Imran 118*
- Qur'an al Araf 179 38 Qur'an Bani-Isra'il 72*
- Acikgenc, A. (1996). *Islamic Science: Towards a Definition*. Kuala Lumpur: ISTAC. P.10
- Iqbal, M. (1944). *The Secrets of the Self: (Asrar-i-Khudi) a Philosophical Poem (Revised ed.)*. (R. A. Nicholson, Ed., & R. A. Nicholson, Trans.) Lahore :
- Sh. M. Ashraf
- B. Laila. <https://groups.yahoo.com/neo/groups/pakistan-home-education> 2012

Author Information

Dr. Samina Saadia

Professor, Sheikh Zayed Islamic Centre, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

Dr. Muhammad Farrukh

Assistant Professor, School of Creative Arts, the University of Lahore, Lahore, Pakistan

Dr. Mohammad Nawaz

Professor, Department of Islamic Studies, the University of Lahore, Lahore, Pakistan

Dr. Zahid Farooq

Lecturer, Department of Islamic Studies, the University of Lahore, Lahore, Pakistan

Dr. Abdul rouf Zahid

Assistant Professor, Department of Islamic Studies, the University of Lahore, Lahore, Pakistan

Dr. Hafiz Zulfiqar Ali

PhD from Department of Islamic Studies, Government College University Lahore, Pakistan
